

Stakeholder Report 2022

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Introduction

After a couple of challenging pandemic years, the doors were once again opened to in-person conference participation in 2022. As you can read below, OAPEN took advantage of this and went to big library events like UKSG Conference, LIBER Conference, OA Tage, and Charleston Library Conference but also other important events throughout the year. It has been exciting and rewarding to meet people in person again while we still benefit from the convenience and efficiency of online meetings.

For OAPEN and DOAB, 2022 was a decisive year in financial terms as we were worried about how the library community would interpret that we had reached our SCOSS target in 2021. Together with the SCOSS team we were careful in our communications: reaching the SCOSS target was great but only the beginning of becoming financially sustainable through institutional investments in our open infrastructures for academic books. All the valuable support we receive from libraries and consortia needs to be sustained through continued support – otherwise we will not be able to uphold our operations.

We have therefore been very pleased to see that almost all of those libraries who had to decide about continued support to OAPEN and DOAB in 2022, have decided to maintain their contribution. We thank all our supporting libraries for their contributions in 2022. We know that library budgets are often tight, that resources are prioritised carefully, and commitments often only made for one year. Although one-year contributions make long-term technical investments less easy, we are grateful that 208 institutions believe that investing in open infrastructures for books is important

and that OAPEN and DOAB are deemed trustworthy recipients of their support.

The number of books added to OAPEN and DOAB keeps growing at high pace and we keep onboarding new publishers. This is great, and it reflects that the momentum for open access to academic books is growing. We have also launched services like our usage statistics dashboard service and PRISM and we have successfully applied for Horizon Europe funding with the [PALOMERA project](#) which will increase our engagement with research funders significantly. To manage all of this we have been fortunate to onboard new people to our team and to set up an advisory board for OAPEN with a broad representation of stakeholders. We are looking ahead to a new and exciting year, building on the many achievements of 2022 featured in this report.

We thank all
our supporting
libraries for their
contributions in
2022

All books and chapters in the OAPEN Library are available for direct download without any cost or registration requirements for the user. In 2022, we have added 7,000 publications to the OAPEN Library, increasing the size of the complete collection to well over 26,000 open access books. In terms of publishers, we welcomed 20 new publishers to the OAPEN Library publisher community, consisting of 420+ publishers now.

Number of downloads

The OAPEN Library is being widely used and accessed by users globally. In 2022, we saw an impressive increase in the number of downloads. During this period, the collection grew from around 19,000 to more than 26,000 books. At the same time, downloads from the OAPEN Library increased in 2022 to well over 12 million COUNTER-conformant downloads for that year.

Downloads worldwide

Languages and licences

Most downloaded books

72,117
[Frankenstein](#)

87,777
[Russkij jazyk konca XX stoletija](#)

33,664
[Primary and Secondary Education During Covid-19](#)

33,213
[Bitcoin and Beyond](#)

29,672
[How the World Changed Social Media](#)

29,471
[International Relations](#)

21,830
[The Malleus Maleficarum and the construction of witchcraft: Theology and popular belief](#)

20,866
[Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling \(PLS-SEM\) Using R](#)

20,104
[Elements of Causal Inference](#)

19,716
[Education and Development in Colonial and Postcolonial Africa](#)

Number of libraries engaging with the OAPEN Library

Taking a closer look at how libraries engage with the OAPEN Library, our analysis showed that when examining data for 2022, over 1,455 academic institutions and libraries have used the OAPEN Library. Patrons at these libraries and academic institutions access the OAPEN Library via the library catalogue, discovery systems, or other third-party systems and routes.

Find out more about the OAPEN Library and how we identify libraries and academic institutions using our services via the following blog post: <https://oapen.hypotheses.org/246>.

Research funders and collections

The OAPEN Library hosts various collections on behalf of research funders. These funder collections have been steadily growing over the years. In 2022, research funder OA book collections managed by the OAPEN Library grew significantly, now including well over 2,450 open access books. As of 2023, we have started a new collaboration with the German Research Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, DFG) and will be adding their collection of open access books to a dedicated DFG funder collection in the OAPEN Library.

Research funder spotlight: The Dutch Research Council (NWO)

Since 2020, the OAPEN Library works together with the Dutch Research Council (NWO), hosting its open access books in the OAPEN Library and providing discovery, preservation, and other services for OA books stemming from NWO-funded research. To date, the [NWO collection](#) includes nearly 200 high quality open access books, a good number of which are made available thanks to a simple and straightforward [open access book programme](#) run by NWO.

During the 2022 International Open Access Week, we organised a special campaign around the open access books from the collection of NWO. As part of this campaign, we carried out interviews with three authors/editors of open access books, which can be found here: [1. Janneke van Bergen](#), [2. Karène Sanchez-Summerer](#), and [3. Rens Bod](#).

In 2023, we look forward to continuing to provide discoverability for these OA books and adding more titles to the growing collection.

Since 2012, the OAPEN Foundation has operated the global indexing service, the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB, <http://doabooks.org>). In 2019, DOAB was created as a not-for-profit Dutch Foundation owned by OAPEN and OpenEdition (<https://www.openedition.org>) through Aix-Marseille University (<https://www.univ-amu.fr/en>) and CNRS (<https://www.cnrs.fr/en>).

Today DOAB indexes over 65,000 peer-reviewed OA books from more than 630 publishers. All metadata in DOAB is distributed fully open (CC0) from its open source DSpace 6 platform in several formats including MARCXML, CSV, RIS, and ONIX. It is also possible to search the directory using the REST API and the directory can be harvested using OAI-PMH.

DOAB is free to use for libraries, publishers, and anyone else. Users don't need to register to explore the richness of the catalogue. Publishers need to comply with basic requirements for peer review and open licensing to have their books indexed in DOAB.

Libraries and other institutions (including research funders) can support the operation and development of DOAB through our supporter programme and publishers can support DOAB through our sponsorship programme. We wish to thank all our supporters and sponsors immensely for their contributions in 2022.

DOAB Supervisory Board and Management

The DOAB Foundation is managed by the Executive Board (Pierre Mounier - Associate Director of OpenEdition and co-coordinator of OPERAS and Niels Stern - Director of OAPEN Foundation) and steered by a Supervisory Board. In 2022, Charles Watkinson joined the Board replacing Lucinda Jones and Marlène Delhaye replaced Fabien Borget. We wish to thank Lucinda and Fabien for their support and engagement and welcome Marlène and Charles. When Bas Savenije leaves the Board in 2023, the gender balance of the Board will be further improved as Bas will be replaced by Antia Wiersma from the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW).

The DOAB Supervisory Board consists of the following members:

Neil Jacobs - Chair (UKRN)
Bas Savenije (OAPEN Foundation)
Lionel Maurel (CNRS)
Charles Watkinson (University of Michigan)
Marlène Delhaye (Aix-Marseille University)

Growth of titles and publishers

Around 18,000 new titles and over 80 new publishers were added to the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) throughout 2022. This resulted in DOAB indexing over 65,000 OA books and chapters from around 630 publishers by the end of the year.

Languages and licences

DOAB Scientific Committee and PRISM

In November 2022, DOAB officially launched its new service to further build trust in peer review and open access academic book publishing. The PRISM (Peer Review Information Service for Monographs) service is provided by DOAB as part of the OPERAS service catalogue.

PRISM is a standardised way for academic publishers to display information about their peer review processes across their entire catalogue. At publisher level, all their peer review processes are visible (as they may have more than one process in use across all their series and titles). At the level of an individual publication, the

peer review process applied to that work is displayed.

PRISM's goal is to provide transparency about the peer review process(es) applied. This helps build trust in open access academic book publishing. A recorded webinar introducing PRISM for publishers in partnership with OPERAS-GER can be found [here](#). You can [read more about PRISM](#) on the DOAB website.

The remit of the [Scientific Committee](#) broadened from PRISM specifically to the whole of DOAB, given that the Committee's scope includes many issues across DOAB, such as acting as a court of arbitration for any disputes.

OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit

[The OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit](#) is a free-to-access, stakeholder-agnostic resource that aims to help authors better understand open access for books, increase trust in open access book publishing, provide reliable and easy-to-find answers to questions from authors, and to provide guidance on the process of publishing an OA book. With the help of a global group of stakeholders from the academic community and scholarly communications organisations, we created this public resource for academic book authors and researchers.

The toolkit has been picked up by institutions around the world and found by users from over 170 countries. In 2022, we added an article on open educational resources (OER) and a search function on the homepage to improve findability. Also, almost all 30+ articles are now

licensed under CC BY and the toolkit has been presented on various events, such as the OASPA conference (find the poster [here](#)). Furthermore, in 2022, we added a section with author success stories including ten new interviews called: [Author success stories](#). This collection of case studies features a group of authors who explain in their own words how publishing their book open access has benefited their work. The authors come from different disciplinary and geographical backgrounds and have published with a range of publishers; they explore different reasons why open access was a successful choice for them.

The toolkit has been presented on various events, such as the OASPA conference 2022

OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit

Free resource: Helping authors better understand open access book publishing

What is it?

~40 articles on topics including:

- Copyright & licensing
- Funding sources
- Mythbusting

Why?

Lack of awareness and common misconceptions about open access (OA) for books form barriers to authors choosing OA.

Global usage

Author success stories

- 10 new interviews
- Different disciplinary & geographical backgrounds
- Submitted by a range of publishers

- Independent, stakeholder-agnostic to build trust
- Easy to use and understand

Publishers - submit your authors' success stories:
i.kruijt@oopen.org | Visit & share the toolkit: oabooks-toolkit.org
 Read author success stories: bit.ly/author-success-stories

Open Access Books Network

In 2022, OAPEN continued its contribution to the Open Access Books Network (**OABN**) by providing one of its three coordinators. The OABN, a space bringing together open access book stakeholders to engage in discussions, events, and find helpful materials, further grew its global community and (online) presence in its third year.

Starting out as a bottom-up initiative, the OABN is now formally supported by OPERAS, as it has become a [Special Interest Group \(SIG\)](#). Thanks to the support of OPERAS, the OABN receives further administrative support to better serve its OA book community and will be able to form stronger links with people and organisations in the European open research landscape. The OABN will continue to organise itself and plan its activities independently as a global network.

This year, the OABN continued to grow its community on the Humanities Commons platform where it has over 415 members, its mailing list seeing 320 subscribers, and a twitter following of 1,250+ followers. Furthermore, we've presented the network and our community building efforts during the LIBER Conference and relaunched our website to further professionalise the OABN as a network – putting more emphasis on who we serve, the activities we organise, and valuable resources that are available for our stakeholders.

Visit the relaunched OABN website:
<https://openaccessbooksnetwork.hcommons.org/>

For 2023, the OABN will contribute to the [PALOMERA](#) project. The PALOMERA project will investigate why open access for books is rarely mandated in funder policies, in a project ranging across geographies, languages, economies, and disci-

plines within the European Research Area (ERA). Furthermore, we anticipate for the OABN to continue to develop itself as an open space for the global open access book community to come together.

Community engagement and communication

Communication activities

OAPEN is an active participant in conversations on open access book publishing around the world. In 2022, we were able to visit and participate in many in-person events again such as conferences, workshops, and webinar sessions. Next to this, OAPEN used its communication channels to inform and engage with its community via blogs, twitter, and mailing lists.

*8 blog posts
12k+ total blog visits*

*830 new followers
12,450 total followers
120k+ total tweet views*

*15 newsletter issues
3,906 total subscribers
245 new subscribers*

22 total events

Library community

The year 2022 earmarked the start of the first DOAB-OAPEN working group. Following library input and discussions, the DOAB-OAPEN Library Working Group for Metadata was created. This library working group, involving experts from various libraries around the world, worked on addressing key issues and challenges that open access books face in relation to metadata. More on the working group and the progress it made in 2022 was shared during our Annual Meeting for Supporting Libraries and can be found [here](#).

In 2022 we organised our Annual Meeting for Supporting Libraries for the second time. Spread out over 3 sessions, we invited our library community of 200+ member libraries to join us for this annual event. During these sessions we shared progress, new developments for libraries, and gathered input, feedback, and ideas for the future direction of our open infrastructures and services.

In total, 40 librarians participated in these sessions providing valuable input for the further development of DOAB & OAPEN. A descriptive report is available publicly [here](#).

Next to this, we became part of the Open Book Collective - which, aims to build new relationships between libraries and OA book publishers and providers, as well as to strengthen existing relationships.

Thanks to the continued engagement of the library community we can continue to improve our infrastructures, address key issues via the working group(s), and develop new projects and services such as the MEMO project and recommender service described below.

In 2022, OAPEN participated in the following groups and forums:

- Common Standards (OPERAS SIG)
- OPERAS Executive Assembly
- OAEU Advisory Board
- OASPA OA Books Interest Group
- Open Book Collective Board of Stewards
- OPERAS Executive Assembly
- OPERAS National Node for the Netherlands
- OPERAS-PLUS
- OPERAS STB (Services and Technology Board)
- SCOSS
- Think.Check.Submit Committee

Conference presentations & events

[Booth, Emma, Pennington, Diane, & Snijder, Ronald. \(2022\). NP2022 - The “Nested Triangle” of Metadata Supply for Open Access Books. NISO Plus 2022 Conference. NISO Plus.](#)

[Stern, N. \(2022\) Developing a peer review information service for monographs. PUBMET 2022.](#)

[Association of University Presses, Stern, N: How to Make Your Open Access Books More Discoverable. 2022.](#)

[Mosterd, T. \(2022\). Open Access Books – Making it Work. Liverpool John Moores University Open Research Week.](#)

[Snijder, R., Meijer, D. \(2022\) Opportunities and challenges for Open Access to books. Science Europe conference on open science.](#)

[Stern, N. \(2022\) Collaborating on Open Access Books Analytics. Charleston Conference.](#)

[Stern, N. \(2022\) PRISM: Developing an information service for monographs together with the publisher community.](#)

[Emery, C., Snijder, R. \(2022\) OA Books Toolkit. OASPA Conference 2022.](#)

[Stern, N: Tips and tricks when publishing books open access, Jisc OA myth busting webinar](#)

[Stern, N., Mosterd, T. \(2022\) Tracking the open access book: what data do research institutions and libraries need in support of their strategies around open access books? UKSG Annual Conference 2022.](#)

[Stern, N.: “Scholarly monographs should also be Open Access, shouldn’t they?” – Guidelines and tools to making books Open Access, OA Week Denmark](#)

[Mosterd, T. \(2022\) Open Scholarly Infrastructures for open access academic books: Enabling discoverability and seamless access to academic books from around the world. F.O.R.M. 2022.](#)

[Morka, A., Barnes, L., Mosterd, T. \(2022\) Community-building in action: The Open Access Books Network.](#)

[Stern, N. \(2022\) Collaborating on dashboards for OA usage. Open Access Tage 2022.](#)

[Morka, A., Proudman, V., Sondervan, J., Gatti, R., Stern, N., Mosterd, T. \(2022\) Now we’ve heard it all! Engaging the community in shaping OA policy for books. UKSG Annual Conference 2022.](#)

[Proudman, V., Felder, F., Lutz, J., Stern, N., Vilen, T., Mesotten, L., Morka, A. \(2022\) From speed dating to long-term relationships: strategies for including support for Open Science Infrastructures into library budgets. UKSG Annual Conference 2022.](#)

[Stern, N. \(2022\) Entwicklung des OA-Buchmarktes aus der „Makroperspektive. Open-Access-Transformation der wissenschaftlichen Buchproduktion aus der Perspektive von Institutionen.](#)

[Wilkinson, L., \(2022\) OPERAS Open Chat: Qualitätssicherung](#)

[Stern, N.: L’Evaluation des Sciences humaines et sociales – PRISM](#)

[Mosterd, T. \(2022\) Tracking the open access book. 13. Bremer Open Access eBook Tage.](#)

[Stern, N.: Open Access and Open Archives initiatives, University of Calicut, India](#)

[Snijder, R., & Mosterd, T. \(2022\). Open access books: Building blocks and policies. Septentrio Conference Series, 1, Article 1.](#)

[Stern, N.: Finnish University Libraries Network \(FUN\). Diamond open access books](#)

[Stern, N.: A Brief Saga of OA Books, SciELO Books 10 Years Jubilee](#)

[Snijder, R. \(2022\). In, out & shake it all about: Ingesting and disseminating OA books through OAPEN and DOAB.](#)

[Stern, N.: ERC Online Workshop on the list of compliant publishers & green open access](#)

Publications

Snijder, R. (2022). OK Computer, what are these books about? – An experiment in large-scale classification of open access books. SocArXiv.

<https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/xdhuq>

Snijder, R. (2022). Big in Japan, Zimbabwe or Brazil – global reach and national preferences for open access books. Insights, 35, Article 0.

<https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.580>

Snijder, R. (2022, August 3). Open access books: A global preference for regional subjects. Impact of Social Sciences.

<https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2022/08/03/open-access-books-a-global-preference-for-regional-subjects/>

Books that are popular in seven countries or more.

Apart from an infrastructure providing services, OAPEN is also a place to do research on open access books and to experiment. We have started several research projects which will – hopefully – lead to interesting results.

MEMO – Metadata Export Module for Open access books

We see an increasing demand for selections of titles based on many different criteria. Furthermore, the users of these titles might have specific metadata requirements. For instance, EBSCO requires a bespoke XML output, while the SCCLC project uses MARC and KBART. To cater to these needs, we are developing a flexible export module.

Recommender service

The large collection of the OAPEN Library allows us to use text mining techniques to create a privacy friendly recommendation service. In cooperation with students of the Stevens Institute of Technology and Eric Hellman of the Free Ebook Foundation, we are building a recommendation service that does not rely on privacy violation but instead utilises the contents of the publications.

TOANI – Transparent Open Access Normalised Index

OAPEN provides usage data for many years, and this is appreciated by publishers and authors alike. However, it is not easy to put these numbers into perspective. Many authors want to understand whether their book has had a large impact. This project is developing a way to answer this question by normalising the data based on transparent rules.

Adding a wing to the Palace Project

The [Palace Project](#) is a platform that provides equitable access to digital knowledge, while bolstering the relationship between libraries and patrons, protecting patron privacy, and enabling libraries to serve all their digital content in a single app. OAPEN supports this project by providing titles. We have selected 10,000 recent open access books from the OAPEN Library written in English or Spanish. The required metadata is currently being prepared and tested, and in 2023 the books will be available through the Palace platform.

New technical features and functionalities

We have been working on further integrating our technical environment. On top of that, we have introduced new features and functionalities.

OAPEN Dashboard

During the UKSG 2022 Annual Conference we officially launched the OAPEN Dashboard service - a new analytics service for our library members, publishers, and funder partners to help them gain a deeper understanding of the usage of open access books. The Dashboard service includes data for the entire OAPEN Library. The OAPEN Dashboard includes unique features and functionalities that allow its users to gain a better sense of the uptake of open access books globally, regionally, and locally. Next to this, users can also look at usage by discipline or apply other filters.

For libraries, the Dashboard can be used to gain insights into both institutional usage (based on IP-ranges) and geolocational usage. While libraries are accustomed to measuring usage based on their IP-ranges, insights into geolocational usage offers another unique functionality helpful for understanding the uptake of open access books. Due to their free nature, readers are not obliged to register and authenticate themselves prior to accessing these books. This enables students, researchers, and readers generally to use these books from home, a local coffee place, or a coworking environment. With this Dashboard, libraries can gain insights into the regional usage of open access books, capturing on- and off-campus usage – setting their preferred radius ranging from 20 to 500 kilometres.

Metadata improvements

This year we have worked on improving the metadata feeds aimed at libraries and publishers. The MARCXML feed – which is based on the [MARC21 standard](#) – is used primarily by libraries. The MARC21 standard contains many options to describe publications, and thus it is quite helpful that the National Acquisitions Group (NAG) and the Southern Universities Purchasing Consortium (SUPC) have created [guide-lines](#) for standardised MARC21 records for print books, eBooks, and eTextbooks. By following this standard, content providers can better support academic libraries. We have now made sure that our MARCXML metadata feed adheres to this standard.

Apart from the MARCXML feed we have also updated our ONIX feed. [ONIX for Books](#) is an XML format for sharing bibliographic data describing both

traditional books and eBooks. Just like MARC21, this standard is very comprehensive. It is also quite rigorous: there are many checks of the content. In order to make sure that our metadata better fits with this standard, we have made several small adjustments to how related ISBNs or funding data are displayed.

GOBI integration

We have also been working with EBSCO to integrate our collection into the GOBI service. The GOBI platform supports libraries with the acquisition of eBooks. Books from the OAPEN Library collection are now visible on the bibliographic record in GOBI, helping libraries see if an OA version of a book is available. GOBI users can find lists of OA eBooks broken out by publisher on the DRM-free and Open Access section of Spotlight Lists in GOBI.

Now Available
through GOBI

Projects

European Research Council, ERC-OAPEN-2019 (finalised successfully)
(<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/964352>)

OPERAS-NL (NL)

University Presses and OA books in NL (supported by OPuS Foundation)

COPIM
(<https://www.copim.ac.uk/>)

TRIPLE
(<https://project.gotriple.eu/>)

SCELC & OAPEN Pilot Project
(<https://scelc.libguides.com/SCELC-OAPEN>)

Open Access eBook Usage (OAeBU) Data Trust pilot project
(https://educopia.org/data_trust/)

TRIPLE: Grant agreement 863420
ERC: Grant agreement 964352
PALOMERA: Grant agreement 101094270

Read more on the next page about:

PALOMERA (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094270>)

OA Book Usage Analytics for Diverse Communities - A Demonstration Project (<https://openknowledge.community/projects/bad-project/>)

OPERAS-PLUS (<https://operas-eu.org/projects/operas-plus/>)

SUES4BOOKS

PALOMERA

In August 2022 the PALOMERA project application to Horizon Europe was successfully selected. OAPEN is the scientific coordinator of this project comprising a consortium of 16 partners. The project will investigate the reasons preventing OA for academic books across geographies, languages, economies, and disciplines within the European Research Area. The project will collect qualitative (incl. interviews, surveys, and use cases) and quantitative data to explain existing challenges and bottlenecks. PALOMERA will use this evidence to provide actionable recommendations and concrete resources to support and coordinate institutional policies for OA books. One of these resources is a knowledge base which will become accessible through the OAPEN OA Books Toolkit and another important resource will be a Funder Forum where research funders will convene to exchange knowledge about open access to books and discuss concrete measures for their implementation.

OA Book Usage Analytics for Diverse Communities - a Demonstration Project

The [Book Analytics Dashboard \(BAD\) Project \(2022-2025\)](#) is focused on creating a sustainable OA book focused analytics service. This service is needed to safeguard and support diversity in the voices, perspectives, geographies, topics, and languages made visible through OA books. Funded by the Mellon Foundation, the BAD project is building on an earlier Mellon-funded initiative: Developing a Pilot Data Trust for OA eBook Usage (2020–2022). In this project we will collaborate with colleagues from Curtin University and Educopia. In addition to scaling workflows, infrastructure, and customer support, the demonstration project is developing a long-term plan for housing, maintenance and funding of the analytics service as a sustainable community infrastructure.

OPERAS-PLUS

OAPEN is taking an active part in OPERAS-PLUS, a 36-month project funded by the Horizon Europe framework Infra-Dev that runs from September 2022 to July 2025. Since OPERAS entered the ESFRI Roadmap in 2021, this grant supports OPERAS in its preparatory phase to become operational as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) in 2028. Specifically, OPERAS-PLUS aims to strengthen the OPERAS governance structure, to develop OPERAS national nodes, as well as OPERAS' portfolio of services. It further aims to maximise OPERAS' impact in the ERA and beyond. OPERAS-PLUS brings together a consortium of 13 partners from 12 countries and is coordinated by Michael Kaiser from the Max Weber Stiftung (Bonn, Germany). More details on OPERAS-PLUS can be found here: <https://operas-eu.org/projects/operas-plus/>

SUES4BOOKS

Following our participation in the [SUES project](#) that provided support to Ukrainian journal editors and publishers, OAPEN is currently part of the steering group of the new project SUES4BOOKS. The Ukrainian academic book sector needs support while the war is ongoing and afterwards, during the period of reconstruction. The first steps are now underway to conduct a needs analysis, engaging with Ukrainian publishers and others in the book trade to prioritise for today and tomorrow. In this phase, partners are being identified, building on the SUES work and our other contacts. The initiating team is made up of the originators of the SUES project and experienced Europeans active in book sector projects as well as working on complex cross-border, multinational EU projects.

OAPEN and the USA

2022 was the year in which OAPEN truly moved beyond the limits of “OA Publishing in European Networks.” Foundational support from the Big Ten Academic Alliance and California Digital Library complemented visionary investments by smaller institutions such as the University of Redlands and Elizabeth City State University. Faculty at universities that are primarily oriented toward undergraduate instruction have found creative ways to use open access books and book chapters to enrich their teaching and move away from expensive textbooks that their students may not be able to afford. Having representation from librarians outside the largest research-intensive institutions brings OAPEN closer to this important community of beneficiaries.

With over 4,000 higher education institutions in the USA, there is plenty of room for growth from the base of ca. 40 institutions that supported the OAPEN Foundation during the year. An intensive program of site visits by the Director in the summer and autumn of 2022 increased awareness among publishers, librarians, and funders, and culminated in presentations at the Association of University Presses meeting in Washington, DC, and the Charleston Library Conference in Charleston, SC - two major events of the year. Open access books were a major topic of discussion amongst the almost 1,500 delegates meeting again in person at Charleston. For 2023, OAPEN plans to expand its presence at the Charleston Conference, this time having an exhibitor booth.

The White House Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) has designated 2023 as the Year of Open Science. Investments in the infrastructure that supports digital, open scholarship are at the forefront of national discussions, with the smaller federal agencies that support humanities and social science research required to publish open access policies in August 2023. The PALOMERA project is particularly timely, as US funders seek connection with their European and US counterparts. Ensuring that books and, by extension, the humanities are not left behind in the move to openness has become a priority among US libraries and publishers. OAPEN is well-situated as a central point for strategic planning because of being agnostic as to the business model or type of publisher.

OAPEN’s move into products that provide information and connection, rather than just technology, responds to the need for “the book” to have a strong voice in an open policy landscape that is dominated by the concerns of large science journal publishers. The theme of “bibliodiversity,” developed in South America and spread through Europe, is gaining traction in the US. Regional identity, disciplinary focus, and multilingualism are all features of the US book publishing landscape. It is increasingly recognized in the US that OAPEN can play a crucial role in ensuring that the works of small, not only large, publishers are discovered and recognized.

Charles Watkinson

*Associate University Librarian, Publishing, University of Michigan Library and
Director of University of Michigan Press*

The OAPEN Foundation is a not-for-profit organisation based in the Netherlands, with its registered office at the National Library in The Hague. OAPEN is dedicated to open access, peer-reviewed books.

OAPEN Board of Directors

The OAPEN Foundation is managed by a Board of Directors which consists of the following members:

- Bas Savenije (Chair)
- Kurt De Belder (Secretary) – Leiden University
- Reinier Groen (Treasurer)
- Antia Wiersma – Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences
- Lidia Borrell-Damià – Science Europe
- Charles Watkinson – University of Michigan

OAPEN Advisory Board

The OAPEN Advisory Board provides the Board of Directors with solicited and unsolicited advice on the business matters of OAPEN. The Advisory Board also has the right to render a binding nomination for one member of the OAPEN Board of Directors.

The Advisory Board comprises members from different stakeholder groups and geographical regions. In 2022, we welcomed Cameron Neylon to the Advisory

Board and Brian Hole has replaced Carsten Buhr (De Gruyter).

As of 1 January 2023, the members are:

- Dirk Pieper, Deputy Director, Bielefeld University Library
- Natalia Grygierczyk, Director, Radboud University Press
- Claire Redhead, Director, OASPA
- Regula Graf, Scientific Officer, Swiss National Science Foundation
- Wendy Queen, Director, Project MUSE
- Marin Dacos, National Open Science Coordinator, Ministry of Science
- Brian Hole, CEO, Ubiquity Press/De Gruyter
- Agnès Ponsati, CSIC-Unit of Information Resources for Research, Director (Spanish National Research Council)
- Cameron Neylon, Professor of Research Communications, Curtin University, Co-lead COKI

OAPEN operates three platforms:

- OAPEN Library - a central repository for hosting and disseminating OA books
- OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit - a toolkit on OA book publishing for authors
- Directory of Open Access Books - a discovery service indexing OA books, in partnership with OpenEdition

OAPEN Team

In 2022, we welcomed two new colleagues to the OAPEN team, Laura J. Wilkinson and Laura Bandura-Morgan.

Laura J. Wilkinson joined OAPEN as a Project Manager. Her previous experience includes roles at Crossref, ORCID, UKSG Committee, and at the university libraries of Northumbria, Sunderland, and Oxford.

Laura Bandura-Morgan joined OAPEN as Funder Relations Manager. Laura received her Ph.D in Molecular Biology but for the last 8 years she has been involved in Open Science activities.

The OAPEN team as of 1 January 2023:

- Niels Stern, Director – stern@oopen.org
- Ronald Snijder, CTO/Head of research – r.snijder@oopen.org
- Lotte van Aalten, Publisher Relations Manager – l.vanaalten@oopen.org
- Dorien van der Giessen, Collection Manager – d.vandergiessen@oopen.org
- Tom Mosterd, Community Manager – t.mosterd@oopen.org
- Laura J. Wilkinson, Product Manager – l.wilkinson@oopen.org
- Laura Bandura-Morgan, Funder Relations Manager – l.bandura@oopen.org
- Sinziana Păltineanu, Project Manager – s.paltineanu@oopen.org

Thanks to all our supporters

At the end of 2022 OAPEN and DOAB were supported by just over 200 libraries – see [full list of supporting libraries](#). We want to thank all the libraries supporting us. Without their support we could not sustain and develop our services. We are particularly happy to see that the libraries who began supporting us through the SCOSS programme have decided to continue their support beyond the SCOSS campaign. This is essential since the SCOSS campaign provided the very important kick-off for our engagement with libraries, however without the continued support from them we cannot operate. We also want to thank those private funders and donators who have been supporting us in 2022 and the [DOAB sponsors](#) for their continued support. OAPEN also relies on fees charged to publishers and funders for the services we provide, and we want to thank for excellent partnership with all the publishers and funders that we work with.

Generating a surplus in 2022

As not-for-profit organisations, OAPEN and DOAB still have a goal to generate financial surplus. However, the surplus never leaves the organisation, it is always re-invested. It is also important to remember that a Dutch foundation (*stichting*) by law cannot be sold or acquired. The surplus is used for different things, such as building our contingency fund, new technical developments, and upgrading our existing technical infrastructures; as well as employing new colleagues to support our expanding operations and increased engagement with the community. OAPEN and DOAB have been considerably under-staffed for years, and it has long been an explicit goal to create surplus to enable us to hire more people, thus ensuring a resilient and dynamic organisation.

For those supporting our infrastructures, it is important that OAPEN and DOAB are open and transparent organisations following generally accepted principles on governance, sustainability, and insurance. Such principles are formulated in the Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (<https://openscholarlyinfrastructure.org/>).

OAPEN and DOAB adhere to these principles and have performed a POSI self-audit (see <https://oopen.hypotheses.org/524> and <https://openscholarlyinfrastructure.org/posse/>). One of the POSI principles concerns the generation of a financial surplus:

“Goal to generate surplus – organisations which define sustainability based merely on recovering costs are brittle and stagnant. It is not enough to merely survive, it has to be able to adapt and change. To weather economic, social and technological volatility, they need financial resources beyond immediate operating costs.”

The OAPEN Foundation closed the 2022 financial year with a positive result of €103,024. The DOAB Foundation closed the 2022 financial year with a positive result of €96,386.

Allocation of the surplus to a contingency fund

One of the ways in which we can use our surplus is to build a contingency fund in alignment with the POSI principles. One of the principles related to sustainability reads:

“Goal to create contingency fund to support operations for 12 months – a high priority should be generating a contingency fund that can support a complete, orderly wind down (12 months in most cases). This fund should be separate from those allocated to covering operating risk and investment in development.”

OAPEN and DOAB follow this principle by setting aside revenue each year to build its contingency fund. The exact size of and contribution to the contingency fund is decided by the OAPEN and DOAB Boards on a yearly basis based on the result of the annual accounts. For 2022 the boards of the two foundations have decided to allocate the majority of the surplus in contingency funds for the two foundations: In 2022 the OAPEN Foundation Supervisory Board has decided to add €100,000 to its contingency fund. In 2022 the DOAB Foundation Supervisory Board has decided to add €95,000 to its contingency fund..

Outlook 2023

Part of our mission is to build trust in OA book publishing. This includes of course trust in how we operate. We are and have been guided by the [Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure \(POSI\)](#) since they were formulated more than eight years ago. To be more transparent around how we adhere to these principles we will be performing a self-assessment in 2023 as recommended by the authors of POSI. We look forward to discussing our self-assessment with our governing bodies and the community at large.

As the awareness of open access to books increases among libraries around the world, we experience new demands to the way we can deliver books and metadata into library catalogues. This is indeed very exciting and in order to cater to these new demands we will be developing new metadata export modules that enable us to deliver what the libraries ask for in an efficient manner. We look forward to continuing our conversations with libraries around their needs and how we best address them.

Working with publishers is the backbone of both OAPEN and DOAB. Connecting their books with libraries and readers around the world through our infrastructures is key to our work. We feel fortunate and humble that publishers of all sizes and shapes feel confident in trusting their books with us. We do our utmost to ensure reliable and efficient hosting, distribution, and preservation solutions to them. Although we increasingly work with non-European publishers, we could still do more to increase equity in our publisher base by reaching out to

publishers in for example Africa and Asia. We want to ensure that academic open access publishers in those regions also become aware of the services that we provide and how they can engage with them.

OAPEN also provides services to research funders. In 2022 we were very pleased to enter a new service agreement with Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, thereby extending our collaboration with research funders. The PALOMERA project will further strengthen our engagement with research funders. We look very much forward to coordinate conversations and knowledge exchange between research funders across Europe and beyond and to discuss concrete ways in which OAPEN can support the funders managing and monitoring their policies.

Yet another exciting year lies ahead of us. We look forward to continuing our engagement with all OA book stakeholders in 2023.

Niels Stern, *Director*
OAPEN Foundation

Input/Output chart

The publishers and users of our collection are diverse and may have different technical needs. Our current technical environment reflects this diversity. It enables publishers to add their books, chapters, and metadata in a variety of ways. By offering several types of metadata output, we ensure that the OAPEN and DOAB collections reach readers, teachers, researchers, and libraries.

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